

Isoamyl xanthate as a sensitive reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of tin

S. P. Arya*, S. C. Bhatia, A. Bansal and M. Mahajan

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra-136 119, India

E-mail : search@granth.kuk.ernet.in

Manuscript received 16 March 2001, revised 16 July 2001, accepted 15 September 2001

A method for the spectrophotometric determination of tin has been described which involves the extraction of tin(II) xanthate complex into chloroform. The yellow coloured complex shows λ_{\max} at 350 nm. Beer's law is valid over the range 1–20 $\mu\text{g Sn/ml}$ with a Sandell sensitivity of 0.013 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. Interference studies have been carried out. Gun metal and some synthetic samples have been analyzed to test the applicability of the method.

A large number of reagents are available for the spectrophotometric determination of tin¹, but only a few possess high sensitivity and selectivity². Among these reagents, xanthates³ have been introduced in the extractive methods of separation and determination of metal ions. Potassium isoamyl xanthate⁴ has been used for the spectrophotometric determination of many elements. The reagent has been found to give a sensitive reaction with tin(II). In the existing methods⁵ interferences from important elements are encountered. In the present study, optimization of conditions for the quantitative extraction of tin(II) xanthate complex has been worked out apart from the studies involving stoichiometry and obedience of Beer's law. Various synthetic and industrial samples have been analyzed for tin contents.

Results and Discussion

Tin(II) forms a coloured complex with isoamyl xanthate in dilute hydrochloric acid solution which is extracted quantitatively into chloroform. The reagent blank shows strong absorption at 305 nm, but a sharp decrease in absorbance on going towards longer wavelengths is observed. The complex shows λ_{\max} at 350 nm where the blank value is 0.08. Hence, all the absorbance measurements were carried out at 350 nm.

Optimization of different parameters affecting the extraction of tin(II)-xanthate complex was carried out. Preliminary tests indicated the extractability of the complex in chloroform (absorbance 1.48). Other solvents were also found to extract the complex to different degrees (absorbance values in parenthesis) : carbon tetrachloride (1.36), benzene (1.32), *n*-heptane (0.71), methyl isobutyl ketone (0.11), ethyl acetate (0.11) and isoamyl acetate (0.08).

However, isoamyl alcohol, ethyl methyl ketone and *n*-butanol do not extract the complex.

The complex formed in the aqueous phase is unstable. However, the decomposition leading to the oxidation of Sn^{II} to Sn^{IV} can be retarded by the addition of ascorbic acid (0.5 g) and therefore, the extraction is to be performed within 30 s after adding the reagents. The optimum conditions resulting from such studies are : 6–8 ml of (0.1%) isoamyl xanthate solution, 0.05–0.055 *M* HCl, 0.5–2 min of equilibration time and 0.5 g of ascorbic acid. Beer's law is obeyed over the range 1–20 $\mu\text{g Sn/ml}$ giving 0.96 as the value of regression coefficient (*R*) with a Sandell sensitivity of 0.013 $\mu\text{g Sn cm}^{-2}$. The absorbance of the complex remained unchanged for 24 h. Six replicate determinations containing 200 μg of Sn^{II} gave a standard deviation of 3.29%.

Interference studies : The effect of various ions and complexing agents on the extraction of tin(II) xanthate complex was studied. Potassium chloride (0.5 g), potassium sulfate (1 g), thiourea (1 g), ascorbic acid (0.5 g), hydrazine sulfate (0.5 g), sodium nitrate (0.2 g), potassium citrate (50 mg), sodium oxalate (50 mg) and salicylic acid (50 mg) were found to be tolerated within an error of $\pm 0.5\%$. However fluoride, EDTA and phosphate interfered seriously.

Metal ions such as Mo^{VI}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, V^V, Ni^{II} and Bi^{III} gave coloured extracts under the proposed conditions. However, the extraction of these metal ions except that of Mo^{VI} and Co^{II} was prevented by using suitable masking agents. Addition of ascorbic acid (0.5 g) prevented the extraction of Fe^{II}, Fe^{III} and V^V; tartrate (0.1 g) helped in checking the interference of Zr^{IV}, U^{VI}, Ag^I and W^{VI}; EDTA (50 mg) used in the presence of Bi^{III}; and thiourea (0.5 g)

added for masking the reactions of Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} and Sb^{III} . The volume of the reagent solution was increased to 8 ml while analyzing the samples containing Mg^{II} , Th^{IV} , As^{V} , Be^{II} , Sr^{II} and Hg^{II} . The tolerance limits (within an error $\pm 1\%$) found for different cations are : 50 mg of Al^{III} ; 20 mg of Mg^{II} ; 10 mg each of Mn^{II} , Ca^{II} , Ba^{II} and Sr^{II} ; 5 mg each of Ce^{IV} , Zn^{II} , Th^{IV} and V^{V} ; 4 mg each of Ti^{IV} , $\text{Fe}^{\text{II,III}}$, Cr^{VI} and Be^{II} ; 2 mg each of Hg^{II} and Zr^{IV} ; 1 mg each of U^{VI} , As^{V} and Pb^{II} ; 0.2 mg of Bi^{III} ; 0.1 mg of Ni^{II} and Sb^{III} .

Applications : The proposed method is quite sensitive and selective since most of the analytically important elements such as Fe, Cu, Cr, Bi, Zn, Pb, Ni, Mn, Ti, V and Th were found to be tolerated with the masking of interfering ions by suitable complexing agents. The method is simple and rapid as it takes less than 5 min for a single determination. The applicability of the method was tested by analyzing different synthetic samples and an alloy sample (gun metal) with satisfactory results (Table 1).

Table 1. Analysis of samples by proposed method

Sl. no.	Matrix ^a	Tin added μg	Tin found ^b μg
1.	Al (50)	200	198
2.	Fe (4), Cr (3)	180	181
3.	Ce (5), Th (4)	100	102
4.	U (1), Th (4), Zr (2)	120	121
5.	V (4), Cr (4), Mn (10)	60	59.2
6.	Al (50), Mn (10), Zn (5)	140	140.5
7.	Gun metal ^d	5.5% ^c	5.7%

^aSynthetic samples were prepared by mixing known amounts of metal ion solutions; figure in parenthesis indicates the amount of element in mg.

^bAverage of two determinations. ^cReported value. ^dBritish chemical standard (Cu, 87.8; Zn, 3.9, Pb, 2.8%).

Experimental

A Shimadzu (UV-140-02) spectrophotometer was used.

A stock solution of tin (5 mg ml^{-1}) was prepared by dissolving $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and standardized⁶, lower concentration (100 μg ml^{-1}) was obtained by suitable dilution to give tin(II) solution in 0.5 mol dm^{-3} HCl. The stock solution was kept in a dark place. Stock solutions of other elements were prepared by dissolving their suitable salts in distilled water or in dil. HCl. A 0.1% solution of potassium isoamyl xanthate was prepared in distilled water and kept in dark. Potassium isoamyl xanthate was prepared according to the reported procedure⁷.

Dissolution of gun metal : A sample of gun metal (0.2 g) was treated with 10 M HCl (10 ml) and 16 M HNO_3 (2–4

ml). The contents were heated till the complete dissolution of the sample. After cooling, the volume was made upto 100 ml and analysed by the proposed method.

Procedure : To a solution containing upto 200 μg of tin(II), ascorbic acid (0.5 g) and xanthate solution (6 ml) were added and the volume was made upto 20 ml with distilled water. The complex was extracted for 30 s with chloroform (10 ml). The extract was treated with anhydrous sodium sulfate (0.5 g) for removing the traces of water and the volume was made up to 10 ml with chloroform. The absorbance of the yellow complex was measured at 350 nm against the reagent blank, and tin content was determined.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to express their sincere thanks to Chairman, Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University, for facilities. One of the authors (A.B.) is also thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for providing a Senior Research Fellowship.

References

1. T. Shuyun, S. Zh. Rouyi, H. Louhua and L. Jianjun, *Kuangwu Yan-shi*, 1995, **15**, 105 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1996, **124**, 305831); Z. Zhi-Rong, L. Hui-Wen, C. Wei-Jun, X. Wen-Yuan and P. Dao-Feng, *Guangpu Shiyanshi*, 1999, **16**, 590 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 2000, **132**, 30022); Z. Jian-Wei, L. Shu-Chang and W. Jin-Rong, *Yankuang Ceshi*, 2000, **19**, 173 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 2001, **134**, 36453); C. Bing, Z. Qiangbin, M. Hirotsugu, U. Masayuke and I. Sadanobu, *Anal. Lett.*, 2000, **33**, 2951.
2. Z. Chen, *Kuangye Gangcheng*, 1989, **9**, 45 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1990, **113**, 17058); D. Wang, Z. Xie, Q. Wu, Y. Song and S. Jin, *Analyst (London)*, 1991, **116**, 1189; L. Wenming, M. Weixing, Q. Baohua and Z. Mingxing, *Guangpuxue Guangpu Fenxi.*, 1999, **19**, 765 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 2000, **132**, 160536).
3. K. V. Muralikrishna, B. Polaiah and B. Rangamannar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1993, **70**, 789; B. Polaiah and B. Rangamannar, *Radiochim. Acta.*, 1993, **62**, 99 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1994, **120**, 68265); A. K. Chakravarti, A. Dattagupta, T. Chakravarty, D. C. Mukherjee and S. P. Maulik, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1993, **70**, 230; 1993, **71**, 165; P. R. Chandrasekhar and B. Rangamannar, *J. Radioanal. Nucl. Chem.*, 1995, **200**, 181.
4. A. K. Malik and A. L. J. Rao, *J. Anal. Chem.*, 2000, **55**, 746.
5. N. L. Shestidesyatnaya, N. M. Milyaeva and L. I. Kotelyanskaya, *Zavod. Lab.*, 1975, **41**, 653 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1975, **83**, 201502); Z. Marczenko, "Spectrophotometric Determination of Elements", Wiley, New York, 1976; S. Hara, H. Matsuo and S. Chaki, *Bunseki Kagaku*, 1974, **23**, 1239 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1975, **83**, 21505).
6. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd. ed., Longmans, London, 1961.
7. F. J. Welcher, "Organic Analytical Reagents", Van Nostrand, New York, 1948, Vol. 4.